

GLOBAL CHANGES AND SHOOTING PERIOD CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotation. The article reflects the global changes observed on the planet Earth, and the features of the transition period.

Key words: *Gross national product, ecosphere, ecosphere resources, global geocological destruction, natural ecosphere, non-anthropogenic ecosphere, degradation, ecocentric approach, anthropogenic, geoecosystem.*

Currently, the main indicator of success at the world level or at the level of any country is the growth (or increase) of the gross national product (GNP) [3].

Gross national product does not reflect geo-ecological indicators such as environmental pollution, degradation of natural life systems or deterioration of natural resources. However, in the GNP, economic activities directed at the use of natural resources, such as timber production, mineral extraction, and fishing, are reflected as an indicator of economic growth, but nothing is said about the decrease of natural capital. Such a model of economic growth does not actually prevent the degradation of natural resources, but rather supports it. If population growth is taken into account and the current economic system is maintained, the economy will have to grow 4-5 times in 25-30 years than it is now.

It seems that the limited resources and systems of the ecosphere do not allow this. Conflicts between human society's ever-increasing impact on the ecosphere and the limited size and resources of the Earth can lead to the inevitability of global geocological destruction. Some experts believe that the destruction has already begun, and some believe that humanity will definitely find ways to prevent this destruction.

Humanity has reshaped much of the land, often unconsciously, throughout the history of its economic activities. Especially during the next half-century, enormous

changes took place on Earth, and this process continues today. These changes are interconnected and involve the natural and social layers of the ecosphere.

- The observed global changes on the planet Earth show that the natural ecosphere is gradually transitioning to the anthropogenic ecosphere. Knowing that the ecosphere has sustainability limits, humanity cannot continue to use it recklessly. In the transition period, it is said that humanity will live in good health: either it will learn to live in a new way, that is, within the limits of existing possibilities, or it will degrade and face destruction. In order for humanity to survive and survive, it is necessary to carry out several interrelated transitions of universal importance:

- the process of demographic transition reflects the stagnation of the world population at a relatively low level. According to forecasts, this level is 2 billion. it is most appropriate to be around a person. However, the Cairo Conference of the UN on population problems (1994) based on the current conditions, the highest indicator of the population is 7-8 billion. emphasizes that a person should be around. If the average number of children in all families is 2.1-2.2, the population will not exceed this figure. If later the average number of children in families is less than two, population decline will begin. The population is 2 billion. it will take a concerted effort of all countries over several generations to bring to the people [1];

- the process of economic transition means the transition to the type of "green economy" that takes into account the ecological values (natural wealth, environment, etc.) that are not taken into account by the market today. This type of economy implies the following: the need to perform economic efforts (activity) in accordance with the laws of nature; ecologically fair prices, which include the environmental values that can be taken into account and cannot be taken into account; taxes for the use of environmental pollution, natural resources and life support systems; switch to using only renewable natural resources, etc. In other words, the main task of the economy is to improve the quality of life of people without increasing its scale. The main strategy of the transition economy requires a change from growth to development [2];

- the process of technological transition means the transition from resource-consuming and environmentally polluting technologies to the most environmentally friendly technologies. The amount of resources used and emissions to the environment

is closely related to the population and its consumption. Therefore, the technological transition strategy must be comprehensive and organized;

- means the transition to the highest level of ecological awareness, thinking and ethics based on the ecocentric approach through the pedagogical-ethical transition process (ecological education, upbringing and culture formation) - to the level of extremely responsible attitude to the environment;

- the process of social transition means the transition to a fairly fair distribution of environmental and economic benefits (benefits) within and between nations or nations;

- an orderly transition process determined by society and taking the form of a rule means the transition to effective forms and means of managing environmental security at the national and international levels.

Interrelated implementation of these components of the transition strategy is a necessary condition for preventing or eliminating the global geocological disaster.

Global transition processes further increase the scale of anthropogenic changes in the ecosphere. At the same time, interdependence between countries will increase. The current economic globalization leads to an even greater globalization of geocological problems.

Based on the analysis of the characteristics of the transitional period, the following main problems can be distinguished, which cause environmental, social or political tensions and reduce the level of environmental security:

- increased anthropogenic impact on the ecosphere or geoecosystems, their components;

- sharp decrease in access to natural resources and further complication of problems in this regard;

- growing population and needs in developing countries with a major impact on ecosphere systems;

- rapid growth of the population of cities, inconsistent with the number of optimal jobs and the ecological situation.

Along with geo-ecological problems on a global scale, complex problems on a regional scale are also emerging. For example, the radioactive contamination of the Chernobyl region, the drying up of the Aral Sea and the degradation of the South Aral Sea, the deterioration of the state of forests in the southeastern part of Asia, the intensification of the process of desertification in the Sahara, and the worsening of the environmental situation in the oil and gas region of Western Siberia. The list of such regional problems is extremely long and their number is constantly increasing.

Strategies to prevent global and regional geocological catastrophes or crises require the development and implementation of measures to immediately influence the transitions that are occurring.

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